

Tracer Study on the BS Criminology Graduates of Isabela State University Cabagan

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Abstract:- This study focused on the whereabouts of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BS Crim) graduates in terms of their employment status, competencies learned, relevance of their degree and trainings and their perception with the different services offered by the University which will serve as basis for revision or enhancement of the program. A total of 611 respondents out of 959 graduates served as respondents of the study. The graduates have high rate of employability in law enforcement, armed forces, security management and administration. The graduates are equipped with human or interpersonal as well as communication skills. The graduates recognized the need for entrepreneurial skills since this course was not imbedded on their curriculum and also the improvement of housing and dormitories. Descriptive method was used in analyzing and interpreting the data.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education today must go beyond the academic. It must focus on providing the skills, knowledge and values that enable graduates to contribute meaningfully to accelerate economic, political, spiritual, and social development and thus enhance their role in society as responsible and productive citizens. The enhancement of education's well rounded function results in economic growth, which helps generate more funds for educational development (*Commission of Higher Education*).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering the Criminology program are envisioned as significant educational institutions actively and continually involved in producing graduates who have the knowledge and skills in addressing the problem of criminality in the country and the competence to meet the challenge of globalization in the field of Criminology. The field of criminology is advanced theoretical field of studies. It is a study of crime and the various agencies of justice as they operate and react to crime, criminals and victims. It is therefore a mission of the Criminology Program to provide the community with professionally competent and morally upright graduates who can deliver efficient and effective services in crime prevention, crime detection and investigation, law enforcement and custody and rehabilitation of offenders, among others (*CMO No. 21, series of 2005*). The Bachelor of Science in Criminology is a four-year college degree program intended for individuals who wish to have a career in the fields of Law Enforcement, Security Administration, Crime Detection and Prevention and Correctional Administration.

The Isabela State University-Cabagan Campus through the Department of Social Sciences under College of Development Communication and Arts & Sciences enabled the offering of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology in the year 2006 by virtue of the Board of Regents Resolution Number 14, series of 2006 with specific objectives to its graduates to manifest the value of leadership, integrity, accountability and responsibility while serving their fellowmen, community and country; be ready to career in the crime prevention, law enforcement, scientific crime detection and correctional administration; conduct research and inquiry on the nature, causes, treatment or punishment of criminal behavior and how criminal justice agencies respond to crime, criminal and victims; implement criminal law, special laws, forensic laws and other similar laws; be equipped with fundamentals of criminal investigation; be knowledgeable in the fields of Criminalistics such as Police Photography, Dactyloscopy, Questioned Documents Examination, Polygraphy, Ballistics, Forensic Science and Toxicology. Within a decade of its existence, the criminology program had produced eleven (11) batches of graduates from the year 2010 to 2020.

Alumni tracer studies are the most important vehicle to build strong bonds between the alma mater and the ever-increasing graduates. This is feasible in two perspectives. First, the alumni are the rich source of feedbacks for improvement in the course curriculum, teaching methods, research, extension, and networking. On the other hand, tracer study helps to measure the extent of professional and academic careers pursued by the graduates after gaining knowledge and skill through academic institutions like Isabela State University.

The findings of the study are beneficial foremost to the students and would-be students of the program as the information that generated from the respondents will be used to improve its curricula to fit to the situation in the industry. Program coordinators and faculty members will be benefited also as the outcomes would provide insights on their competencies and thereby lead them to adopt more effective and quality teaching methods, strategies and it will provide the necessary information as to the strengths and weaknesses of the prospective graduates of the program. Campus management will also benefit from the results as it would provide information which may serve as guide for planning to a meaningful and effective criminology program. The result would provide also feedbacks to help them examine respective program offerings as well as different student services offered by the university. In addition, the offering of allied academic programs might be considered based on the demand courses that will be identified by the alumni.

At present, there were no available data to determine the whereabouts & status of employment of the alumni, evaluate the relevance of their education & training undertaken and also their feedbacks on the student services of the university hence, this study was conceptualized.

II. OBJECTIVES

The study aimed to trace the whereabouts of the graduates of the program. Specifically, the researchers sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a) Age
 - b) Sex
 - c) Civil Status
 - d) Dialect
 - e) Educational Attainment
 - f) Eligibility
2. What is the status of employment of the respondents in terms of:
 - a) Rate of employability
 - b) Type of employment
 - c) Length of time in looking for a job
 - d) Reasons for delay of employment
 - e) Factors that facilitated them in getting their first/present job
 - f) Monthly salary
 - g) Relevance of course/training to their present job
 - h) Competencies learned in college that they find useful in their job
3. What are the feedbacks of the respondents on the student services of the university in terms of?
 - a) Curriculum/course content
 - b) Methods of Instruction
 - c) Faculty
 - d) Library
 - e) Laboratories
 - f) Physical Plant
 - g) Career Guidance
 - h) Housing/Dormitories
 - i) Job Placement
 - j) Academic Counseling
 - k) Research Services
 - l) Extension Services

III. METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive method of research. The respondents of the study were graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology program from the year 2010 to 2019. The questionnaire was patterned from the format of the University Quality Assurance Office and CHED. However, modifications and enhancements were done to address the specific concerns of the program under study. The researcher obtained the names of graduates from the registrar and likewise asked their permission before the gathering of data. The researcher personally visited their respective houses and offices of the graduates but mostly through goggle forms, e-mails and social networking sites. Simple frequency count, percentage and weighted mean were utilized in the study. Likert scale was also used in the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the data gathered, analysis, interpretation and discussion of data.

	Frequency	Percentage
1.1 Age		
22	37	6.06
23	57	9.33
24	60	9.82
25	79	12.93
26	70	11.46
27	78	12.77
28	74	12.11
29	40	6.55
30 above	116	18.99
1.2 Sex		
Male	483	79.05
Female	128	20.95
1.3 Civil Status		
Single	270	44.19
Married	341	55.81
1.4 Dialect		
Single	270	44.19
Married	341	55.81
Ibanag	570	93.29
Ilocano	41	6.71
1.5 Educational Attainment		
BS	607	99.35
MS	1	0.16
Ph.D (on-going)	1	0.16
LLB (on-going)	2	0.33
1.6 Eligibilities		
Board Exam (RA6506)	546	89.36
Civil Service Exam	2	0.33
PO1 entrance exam	2	0.33
PD 907	4	0.65
AFP entrance exam	11	1.80
None	58	9.49

Table 1: frequency and percentage of respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, dialect, educational attainment and eligibilities

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, dialect, educational attainment and eligibilities. Based on the result, Table 1.1 reveals that majority of the respondents are 30 years old and above having 18.99% and the least are those 22 years old which is only 6.06%. It also shows that majority are male having 79.05% while female is 20.95% as indicated in Table 1.2. This means that the Criminology program was dominated by male graduates. In Table 1.3, it shows that most of the respondents are married having 55.81% while single respondents are 44.19%. Table 1.4 also reveals that graduates are mostly Ibanag having 93.29% while Ilocano respondents are 6.71%. This means that, enrollees of the program are mostly within the municipality

of Cabagan and nearby towns. Under Table 1.5, it shows the distribution of the respondents in terms of their Educational Attainment. Based on the data, most of the respondents are Bachelor's Degree holder having 99.35% while MS and on-going Ph.D. holders tied at 0.16%. This implies that graduates of the program didn't yet pursue higher degree before or while having their job. Majority of the respondents are Board Exam passers with 89.36% while CS and PO1 entrance exam tied at 0.33%. as shown in Table 1.6. It implies that the program has very good curriculum, quality instruction and faculty members. It also reveals that graduates of the program are very qualified before looking into their job.

Rate of Employability	Frequency	Percentage
Employed	593	97.05
Self Employed	8	1.31
OFW	10	1.64
Total	611	100

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to Rate of Employability

Table 2 reveals that most of the respondents are employed with 97.05% while self-employed is only 1.31%. It implies that the program has high rate of employability

and produced quality graduates which are now connected with various agencies.

Nature of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
PNP	493	80.69
AFP	15	2.45
BJMP	8	1.31
BFP	2	0.33
BUCOR	1	0.16
PCG	1	0.16
LTO	3	0.49
COURT	2	0.33
DILG (Contact Tracer)	24	3.93
SECURITY AGENCIES	19	3.11
ACADEME	7	1.15
MALLS/SUPERMARKET	11	1.80
LGU (staff)	4	0.65
Barangay (Kagawad/SK Chairman)	3	0.49
Others (OFW & Self Employed)	18	2.95
Total	611	100

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to Nature of Employment

Table 3 shows the distribution of the respondents in terms of their company. Based on the data, majority of the respondents are members of the Philippine National Police

having 80.69 % while BUCOR and PCG tied at 0.16%. This implies that jobs of the graduates are in line with their finished degree or training.

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Permanent	509	83.31
Temporary/Casual	19	3.11
COS/JO	80	13.09
Others(self-employed)	3	0.49
Total	611	100

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to Employment Status

Table 4 shows that most of the respondents are under permanent status with 83.31 % while self-employed are only

0.49%. It implies that the graduates of the program have secured their tenure on their job.

Monthly Salary	Frequency	Percentage
5,000-9,999	6	0.98
10,000-14,999	18	2.95
15,000-19,999	36	5.89
20,000-24,999	16	2.62
25,000-29,999	13	2.13
35,000 -39,999	513	83.96
40,000 -44,999	8	1.31
50,000 -54,999	1	0.16
Total	611	100

Table 5: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to their Monthly Salary

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents have 35,000 -39,999 monthly salary with 83.96 % and only one respondent has 50,000-54,999 with 0.16%. This implies that

graduates of the program are categorized under lower middle class in the society (*Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2021*).

Length of time looking for a Job	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1 year	99	16.20
1-2 years	265	43.37
2-3 years	176	28.81
3-4 years	37	6.06
4 years & above	34	5.56
Total	611	100

Table 6: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to the Length of time in looking for a job

Table 6 reveals that most of the respondents took only 1-2 years in looking for a job with 43.37% while the least took 4 years and above before landing into a job with 5.56-

%.This implies that the program have quality graduates and also aligned with the demands of the industry because of short timeline in landing for a job.

Reasons for the Delay of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Delay of Issuance of School credentials	12	1.96
Delay in taking/passing the board exam	19	3.11
Delay of the issuance of other needed documents	8	1.31
No immediate vacancy	230	37.64
Tight competition for the job.	234	38.30
Available job/s are not in line with specialization	6	0.98
Lack of financial support for job hunting	153	25.04
Health reasons	1	0.16
Early marriage	2	0.33
Not emotionally ready	4	0.65
Due to Pandemic	25	4.09

Table 7: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to their Reasons for the Delay of Employment

Table 7 shows the distribution of the respondents in terms of their reasons for the delay of their employment. Based on the data, it reveals that main reason is the tight of competition for the job with 38.30% and the least reason is

health reason with 0.16%. This means that graduates of the program are aligned with the demands of the industry and also they are physically and mentally fit while looking for a job.

Factors that facilitated you in getting your First/Present job	Frequency	Percentage
Educational Qualifications	568	92.96
Assistance of the ISU's Placement office	3	0.49
Government employment office	26	4.26
Media advertisement	16	2.62
Recommendations from relatives/friends	2	0.33
Recommendations from former teacher	3	0.49
Personnel office of the company	25	4.09
Job fair/DOLE	4	0.65
On line applications	53	8.67

Table 8: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to the Factors that facilitated them in getting their first Job/Present Job

Table 8 shows that the respondents' main factor in landing for the job is their educational qualification with 92.96% and the least factor is the recommendation from

relatives or friends with 0.33%. It implies that graduates of the program are very qualified and competitive as they are looking for a job.

Relevance of College Degree/Training in your present job	Frequency	Percentage
Very Relevant	577	94.44
Relevant	9	1.47
Fairly Relevant	25	4.09
Poor	0	0

Table 9: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to the Relevance of College Degree/Training in your Present Job

Table 9 shows the distribution of the respondents according to the relevance of their degree and training. Based on the data, it reveals that 577 or 94.44 % said that it is very relevant and only 9 or 1.47% said that it is relevant.

The above data implies that their degree and trainings undertaken are aligned with their chosen field of specialization.

Competencies	Male		Female		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Communication Skills	329	53.85	114	18.66	443	72.5
Human Relation/Interpersonal Skills	407	66.61	113	18.95	520	85.11
Leadership Skills	146	23.90	81	13.26	227	37.15
Entrepreneurial Skills	41	6.71	30	4.91	71	11.62
Information Skills	120	19.64	82	13.42	202	33.06
Problem Solving Skills	58	9.49	36	5.89	94	15.38
Critical Thinking Skills	115	18.82	42	6.87	157	25.70
Research and Extension Skills	222	36.33	121	19.80	343	56.13

Table 10: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to Competencies Learned

Table 10 shows the distribution of the respondents according to Competencies Learned. Based on the data, it reveals that most of the respondents learned human relation or interpersonal skills with 85.11% while the least is in entrepreneurial skills with 11.62%. This implies that

graduates of the program don't have entrepreneurial course as regard to their curriculum and it is now being addressed by the University with the addition of entrepreneurial management in all program offerings.

Students Services	Excellent		Very Good		Good		Fair		Needs Improvement		Mean	Description
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F		
1. Curriculum/Course Content	3.09	0.79	3.88	0.54	0.20	0.74	0.11	0.01	0.12	0.00	4.74	Excellent
2. Methods of Instruction	3.09	0.74	3.82	0.60	0.25	0.85	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.00	4.74	Excellent
3. Faculty	3.50	0.77	4.27	0.33	0.22	0.55	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	4.85	Excellent
4. Library	0.39	0.15	0.54	1.68	0.37	2.05	0.67	0.21	0.87	0.09	3.61	Very Good
5. Laboratories	0.51	0.16	0.67	1.01	0.35	1.36	1.10	0.24	1.34	0.14	3.53	Very Good
6. Physical Plant	0.74	0.20	0.95	1.32	0.39	1.71	0.86	0.20	1.07	0.05	3.78	Very Good
7. Career Guidance	1.19	0.30	1.50	1.51	0.46	1.97	0.47	0.10	0.57	0.04	4.07	Very Good
8. Housing/Dormitories	0.25	0.06	0.30	1.01	0.16	1.17	1.00	0.26	1.26	0.22	3.10	Good
9. Job Placement	1.55	0.34	1.90	1.41	0.39	1.79	0.31	0.12	0.44	0.05	4.18	Very Good
10. Academic Counseling	1.10	0.19	1.29	1.70	0.50	2.19	0.41	0.13	0.54	0.02	4.05	Very Good
11. Research Services	1.06	0.29	1.34	1.72	0.39	2.11	0.42	0.16	0.58	0.02	4.05	Very Good
12. Extension Services	1.32	0.24	1.55	1.71	0.48	2.19	0.29	0.12	0.42	0.00	4.17	Very Good
Overall Mean											4.07	Very Good

Table 11: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to their feedbacks in Student Services of the University

Table 11 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their perception with regards to student services offered by the university. Based on the data, it reveals that faculty area obtained the highest mean which is

4.85 or excellent and the lowest mean is in housing and dormitories which is 3.10 or good. This implies that there is a quality of good services being offered by the University.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- Most of the respondents are 30 years old and above.
- The graduates of the Criminology program are dominated by male.
- Most of the graduates are married and Ibanag.
- Majority of the graduates are Bachelor's degree holder and few have finished MS degree and earned Ph.D. units
- With the sample, majority of the graduates are registered criminologist, AFP entrance exam passers and few are Civil Service eligible.
- Majority of the graduates are employed and holding permanent status while few are temporary or casual.
- Most of the graduates became police officers and soldiers. Other graduates also landed in job not related to their profession like OFW, tellers and dizers.
- Most of the graduates landed to their job within one to years after graduation.
- Majority of the graduates received an income ranging from 35,000-39,999 and only one is receiving 50,000-54,999.
- Most of the graduates revealed that the main reasons for the delay of their employment are the tight of competition for their job and no immediate vacancy while only one mentioned about health reason.
- Majority of the graduates stated that their educational qualification is the main factor why they landed into their job and only few said that it is because of the recommendation from a relative or friend.
- Most of the graduates revealed that their college degree and training are very relevant to their job and only few said that it is relevant.
- Majority of the graduates found that human/interpersonal, communication research and extension, leadership, information and critical thinking are the most important and useful skills into their job.
- The graduates revealed that student services in the area of faculty, curriculum and method of instruction are excellent while there is a need for the improvement of housing and dormitories which is only good.

VI. CONCLUSION

- The Criminology profession is a male dominated course
- There is a high rate of employability in the field of law enforcement, armed forces, security and majority of them holding permanent status.
- There is a low rate of graduates who pursued graduate studies.
- The knowledge acquired by most of the graduates matched their jobs.
- There is a proof that criminology graduates are very competitive and also they are physically and mentally prepared while looking for a job.
- The graduates are not adequately equipped with knowledge and exposure in entrepreneurial skills since they don't have entrepreneurial course imbedded in their curriculum.

- There is a proof of excellence in instruction, curriculum and faculty because of the number of registered criminologist produced by the program.
- For the welfare of the students, there is quality of good services being offered by the University

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Encouraged more female enrollees to the criminology program.
- Faculty members must encouraged future criminologist to apply in other law enforcement agencies aside from PNP.
- Faculty members must also encouraged future criminologist to pursue graduate studies for them to grow professionally in their chosen field of specialization.
- The criminology program must to continue its strategies in providing quality and excellence in instruction and faculty to produce more registered professionals.
- Entrepreneurial course must to be imbedded in the curriculum for the graduates to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills.
- There is a need for the improvement on the services being offered by the campus in terms of Housing and Dormitories.

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